

ICTs in education for Deaf and Hard-Of-Hearing learners

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World Journal of Biology Pharmacy and Health Sciences, 2023, 14(03), 222–236

Publication history: Received on 08 May 2023; revised on 19 June 2023; accepted on 21 June 2023

Article DOI: <https://doi.org/10.30574/wjbphs.2023.14.3.0273>

Abstract

This study is a literature review which focuses on the educational needs for the deaf and DHH and the various environments that are available for them, based on ICTs. Most of the reviewed articles are quantitative researches (Survey Research, Experimental Research Design), focused on the effectiveness and the design of the applications and programs that contribute to the communication, as well as the education of deaf and DHH students. Other articles that were studied are literature reviews addressing the educational needs, ICT based tools, as well as suggesting necessary future improvements for this educational approach.

Keywords: Disabled; Deaf; Hearing Disabilities; Digital Technologies; Inclusion

1. Introduction

Deaf and Hard-of-Hearing (DHH) kids are frequently enrolled in oral programs in mainstream schools, which do not adequately address their educational, social, or emotional requirements. Instead deny them the right to participate in supportive learning environments, such as those that allow for visual access to education (Constantinou et al., 2018). Moreover, classes rely on spoken information and communication, so sign language is typically not an option in mainstream classrooms. This demonstrates that is difficult for instructors and other peers to understand as well as communicate with Deaf and Hard-of-Hearing students (DeWitt et al., 2015).

Even when a sign language expert is present in the regular classroom, he/she is frequently not a teacher and might not be able to accurately translate the instructor's lectures for the student, leading to yet another instance of poor communication (Hyde et al., 2009). Because verbal contact between students and their instructor is the most crucial component of typical classroom, many Deaf and Hard-of-Hear students miss out the chance to learn. For students with hearing loss, there is a need for educational institutions that effectively utilize visual learning equipment, adaptive devices such FM systems, and speech-to-text transcription (Constantinou et al., 2018).

In addition, more of these kids are attending mainstream schools thanks to advancements in universal screening and sensory assistance technologies (such cochlear implants) (Kelman & Branco, 2009). It is crucial to concentrate on the abilities needed by the teachers and staff, such as adaptability, technology changes, and ongoing professional development, to meet the children's educational and emotional needs while also providing an environment that meets their psycho-social requirements. It will be difficult to provide services that are tailored to each child's requirements and take into consideration their skills, aspirations, and attitudes (De Raeve, 2010). However, it is also important to consider the unique demands of deaf students and offer flexibility in satisfying those needs (Constantinou et al., 2018).

An additional study of Drigas et al. (2009), which looked at the reasons why deaf individuals use the internet, was carried out by creating and distributing an online questionnaire to the members of two deaf organizations in Athens. The focus of this project is understanding the needs and preferences of the deaf community with regard to the

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informational and communicational capabilities of new technologies, as well as whether these capabilities support the active social and economic participation of those who have hearing loss.

The goal of the aforementioned study (Drigas et al., 2009), is to clarify that the usage of the internet has substantially enhanced deaf people's ability to inform themselves and communicate. Greater social engagement results from improved communication since it is easier to influence social change while communicating with others. Better knowledge, on the other hand, refers to a greater understanding of the environment, concepts, values, and societal orientation. The internet's extensions and applications, which provide an open framework for communication, enable deaf people to make clear contact with all potential listeners, whether they are deaf or not. This effectively ends the social isolation and exclusion of deaf people from social life and activities.

2. The inclusion of ICTs in the educational approaches for the deaf and hard-of-hearing

In the past years, the social inclusion of individuals with disabilities has been a popular topic, and an increasing database of studies suggests ICTs offer the deaf new opportunities (Glaser and Tucker, 2004). Deaf and hard of hearing people's inclusion and engagement in society can be improved by using ICTs, according to a variety of researchers (Drigas et al., 2004; Drigas et al., 2005; Drigas et al., 2006; Barak& Sadovsky, 2008; Power& Power, 2009; Drigas et al., 2010).

According to Zaharudin et al. (2011) their research findings demonstrated that Deaf students have no difficulty interconnecting with computer-based learning materials. Deaf Students don't think twice to participate when there is a misunderstanding. Most educators accept that ICT courses supplied to deaf students are extremely adaptable to them.

The use of video technologies can greatly improve communication between Deaf individuals whose primary language is sign language. The selection of the technically complex video in the e-learning system is crucial. It is necessary to have a way for evaluating a system's utility when choosing or creating sign language communication systems. For deaf individuals, enhanced connectivity via video offers many advantages.

Learning games should be designed in a way to convert auditory inputs in a deaf-friendly visual modality, to make learning games accessible for DHH users. The incorporation of written text and sign language translation into the game design are two potential options that may be helpful to overcome language and communication obstacles (Westin et al., 2022).

Despite some difficulties, Augmented reality (AR) games offer positive changes in the educational field, with various sign languages for DHH children. Studies regarding AR-based educational games for DHH and particularly deaf children, seem to be lacking in current research or are less investigated, compared to studies about AR games for learning and for DHH individuals in general (Westin et al., 2022).

3. E-learning and teleeducation

E-learning tools can be used to create a distance and life-long training environment for deaf persons in the e-commerce and new technologies industry. Thereby, e-learning tools can encourage Deaf people's equal rights to access and participation in professional training. They can also provide them with a pathway into the new professional domains through their training in specific knowledge and skill sets related to the usage of the rapidly evolving e-learning and e-commerce industries (Drigas et al., 2004). E-learning also enables the "anytime-anyplace" learning environment for deaf students as they can access tutorials, notes, slides, and other materials at their own pace (Zaharudin et al., 2011)

The term "Education 2.0" refers to the changes that technology has made to the educational landscape, using Web 2.0 tools (Alexander, 2006). The use of Web 2.0 tools promotes the growth of new competencies among students as well as more collaborative and creative learning and scaffolding. Online mind maps, which can also be used in synchronous collaboration, are one example of an ICT application that implements learning theories and didactical models for e-learning. As new e-learning trends have evolved in the era of e-learning 2.0, courses are primarily delivered through learning management systems, including the usage of social networks, wikis, and blogs (Carr et al., 2008).

Another online course for teaching foreign languages to deaf people whose first language is sign language was created and developed by Drigas et al. (2010). The course is focused on online readings, video broadcasts, and web 2.0 applications including social networking and blogs. The course, which was created specifically for deaf people, explores the opportunities that e-learning, vodcasting, and web 2.0 tools can provide to improve the learning process and produce more useful learning outcomes.

Weblogs are being used in teaching and learning by an increasing number of educationalists. The usage of blogs improves learning since it enables it to begin when the students begin actively participating and collaborating for a common goal. Blogs have proven to be a flexible and valuable medium that improves social and academic skills development (Seely Brown and Adler 2008).

Teachers regularly use also social networks in the classroom as they encourage students to express their own ideas, facilitates better communication and teamwork, improves the learning experiences of students, and creates an online learning community. Thus, with the rise of social networking as a significant trend in education, the phrase "educational networking" was established (Anderson,2007; Dalsgaard, 2008)

4. Technology-related programs and activities

Because information is largely presented visually and less audibly in this situation, the Internet and its services significantly lessen the gap between hearing individuals and hard of hearing people (Swain and French, 2004). A hard of hearing individual may access the same depth and variety of information as a hearing person. The most extensive and well-known internet service is the World Wide Web. It is a multimedia service that acts as a built-in foundation for other internet services. (Sanger, 2006).

Drigas et al. (2005) found helpful information about creating accessible HTML sites for the Deaf and hard of hearing on the World Wide Web Consortium (W3C) website. These include:

Synchronized equivalent alternatives with presentations for any time-based multimedia presentation.

Any type of multimedia, whether a movie, animation, or slide show, can be used in a time-based presentation.

Captions, which provide users access to audio tracks, and audio descriptions, which give users access to visual tracks, are equivalent substitutes for these presentations.

It has already been stated that any audio or video track must have a text transcript, as well as a text description of the video track. It is generally acknowledged that on-screen captioning enables Deaf and hard-of-hearing people to enjoy a movie or multimedia production more fully. It must be acknowledged, nevertheless, that a text transcript by itself is not the best way to give people with disabilities an inclusive experience. An after-the-fact separate written transcript does not offer the same kind of experience (Chuck and Geoff, 2000).

4.1. Neural sign reenactor

In order to transfer the body motions, head attitude, and facial expressions of a source actor in a driving video to a target subject in a reference video, Tze et al. (2022) introduced Neural Sign Reenactor, a revolutionary neural rendering pipeline. They have utilized it in the complex situation of sign language videos. Their approach consistently transfers manual and non-manual signals from a source signer to a target signer and is effective among signers of different genders and body types, according to thorough qualitative and quantitative tests. It also generates more realistic and natural appearing outcomes in comparison to prior methods of human motion retargeting that drastically alter the appearance of the target subject. Their work opens the door for the creation of unique sign language production systems that go beyond avatars and create photo-realistic continuous sign language films, enhancing user attractiveness and engagement.

4.2. "DELFE" PROJECT

The learning system (LS) presented in Drigas et al. research (2005) provides Greek Sign Language films that correlate to each text in the learning environment. The system is specifically created for deaf adults in order to support their ongoing vocational and academic training. The LS meets the unique learning demands of Deaf students, including bilingual material (in text and sign language), high levels of visualization, interactive and exploratory learning, and the possibility of peer learning via video conferencing. Greek signers are able to study in their own language—the sign language—for the first time in this setting. In order to meet the aforementioned situation, the LS is customized to the unique learning challenges of the target audience, which consists of deaf teenagers and young adults.

The information offered is bilingual. The use of sign language in the classroom has been demonstrated to dramatically increase reading proficiency in bilingual (spoken and signed language) studies in deaf and hearing-impaired schools. The primary goal of this e-learning environment is to facilitate Deaf people's equal rights to access and actual participation in vocational and educational training.

4.3. "DEDALOS" PROJECT

The primary goal of this project of Drigas et al. (2006) is to encourage Deaf people to learn English as a second language. They have developed a pedagogic technique for remote linguistic training as well as cutting-edge instructional materials that are suitably fitted to the specific team. The entire procedure has been planned and consists of audits and evaluations of the e-student's linguistic abilities. The educational materials have been divided into levels based on the student's prior knowledge. Using an intelligent taxonomy system, the system is intended to evaluate the student and arrange the instructional content at the appropriate level. Quality and creativity of the self-paced learning educational materials, which make extensive use of modern technologies such as animation and digital video into the Sign Language of each partner, have been given special consideration in the design.

4.4. "THETOS" PROJECT

In Poland, THETOS is utilized in medical settings where staff members enter questions. The system then analyzes the questions and determines what animation should be made to convey the same information in Polish Sign Language. A word doesn't necessarily have a "matching sign"; instead, it contains qualities that, when combined, produce a sign. (Suszczanska, 2002).

4.5. "SIGNGUIDE" PROJECT

The main objective of this project (Kosmopoulos et al., 2022) is to create a prototype interactive museum guide system using mobile devices for deaf visitors that will be able to answer questions about the exhibits in the visitors' native language (sign language) and provide additional content in sign language using an avatar or video using methods from the fields of computer vision and machine learning. This study aims to implement and experiment with real users. There are several difficulties to overcome, the most prominent ones being the modeling, translation, and rendering of the continuous SL into an avatar in real-time.

4.6. AR-GAMES

In the twenty-first century, games and game-based learning have developed quickly and widely. Digital games are enticing a sizable portion of the public thanks to the combination of the two categories of intense games and casual games (Juul, 2012). Nevertheless, accessibility for deaf and hard-of-hearing (DHH) individuals remains one of the major obstacles to full inclusion in modern society (Costello et al., 2019). Game designers should try to communicate the content of auditory data in a deaf-friendly visual modality in order to make learning games accessible for DHH users. The incorporation of written text and sign language translation into the game design are two potential options that may be helpful to overcome language and communication obstacles. They can both be experienced through an intact sensory modality, namely sight, and do not rely on the audio modality, making them both accessible to DHH patients (Westin et al., 2022).

In educational settings with various sign languages for DHH children, augmented reality (AR) games offer chances for developing happy learning. Particularly, the technology known as augmented reality (AR) overlays virtual items on real-world things (Akçayır, 2017). Real-time connection, 3D registration, and the blending of the physical and digital world are its three key characteristics (Azuma, 1997). The application of augmented reality in education might increase student engagement and learning effectiveness (Lee, 2008). The term augmented reality (AR) games describe digital games which can be played in a real-world setting while also adding a virtual overlay to it (Squire and Jan, 2007). It is feasible for gamers to engage with both digital things and real-life people, preventing social isolation (Offermans and Hu, 2013).

Recent research has investigated augmented reality for DHH sufferers for a variety of reasons. Quintero et al. (2019) proposed a way for co-creating AR material utilizing principles for universal design learning. They also did a systematic review of AR for inclusive education, containing several papers regarding DHH. This essay especially addresses AR studies for DHH individuals. Parton et al. (2010) conducted a pioneering study on mobile AR for DHH individuals combining 2D barcodes and teacher-produced YouTube videos to build an accessible and workable AR-based learning environment on early cellphones. Earlier study was done by Zainuddin et al. (2010) who created an alternate language AR book for education. The book's content, which was written in Bahasa Malaysia and English, was supplemented by AR videos of sign language and 3D models for illustration.

A mobile AR software developed by Al-Megren and Almutairi (2018) that maps written words to associated signs for learning ArSL has been demonstrated to be more successful than conventional teaching methods that use ArSL, visuals, and fingerspelling. Using a cheap pair of AR glasses, Ridha and Shehieb (2021) developed a system with real-time transcription, voice emotion detection, sound indication features, and classroom assistance capabilities. For usage in

schools, Luo et al. (2022) developed Avatar Interpreter, a real-time sign language interpretation visualization application for head-mounted AR.

Augmented reality (AR) is more intriguing and engaging than traditional learning, particularly when it comes to games. The learning mechanics of augmented reality games include group problem-solving activities, competitiveness, and sharing of experiences, not only between students but also between students and teachers (Li et.al., 2017).

The educational program CopyCat enables deaf children to interact with the computer using ASL and motivates them to practice signing in a fun manner. The child is instructed to wear colored gloves with wrist-mounted accelerometers and place themselves in front of the computer that has a video camera for computer vision recognition system" (Lee et al., 2005). In initial testing, kids quickly figured out when to press the "attention button" to make the computer begin to observe them sign, and the wireless accelerometers didn't bother them.

5. Applications

Enhancing deaf people's access to communication can raise their educational attainment and professional performance while also boosting their independence and self-assurance in carrying out daily duties. A small number of studies have looked at deaf people's communication problems and offered advice to those creating mobile apps. Deaf persons can use smartphones to communicate with those around them(Alnfai et. al., 2018). Some modern communication applications are presented below:

5.1. ROGERVOICE

The world's first mobile app, RogerVoice, translates mobile voice calls into a significantly more accessible form of text in order to provide subtitles for phone conversations. Olivier Jeannel, a deaf engineer, created it. The program converts voice to text using speech recognition technology so that hearing impaired persons may read what the other person is saying. The program was developed as a result of a successful Kickstarter campaign; a beta version of the program is presently accessible and is possible downloaded via the RogerVoice website (Koshtura et.al., 2021).

5.2. LIVE TRANSCRIBE

The program reads spoken words and converts them into text. The program accomplishes this using a smartphone microphone and Google's language API, which supports more than 70 different languages. Making sure the recording is as error-free as possible is the responsibility of machine learning technology. However, Live Transcribe can not only decode the voice, but it can also alert the user that someone is trying to speak to him. It also enables you to take part in the conversation immediately by responding with the built-in keyboard. The Android phone's microphone picks up the spoken text, which is then sent to the device's screen through Wi-Fi or another network connection. When attending conferences or seminars, for instance, this may be helpful for those who cannot hear. The individual who possesses the applications' phones will display spoken words (Koshtura et. al., 2021).

5.3. MYEAR

Gerald Isobe, a deaf golfer, and his son Brandon created the MyEar app. Gerald learned to read lips as a young child but was frustrated that he could only comprehend 30% of what he said. This tool, which he and others use to interact with their hearing coworkers, friends, and family, was developed in response to these problems. The MyEar app records and interprets anything someone says. It is also suitable to be used in emergency situations (Koshtura et. al., 2021).

5.4. AVA

One of the key motivations behind the creation of AVA was the fact that lip reading might be more challenging among a group of individuals. If a deaf or hearing-impaired person is with a group of friends, he or she can persuade those people to sign up for the service so that the deaf or hearing-impaired person can watch the live broadcast of the group chat. The phone's microphone picks up the language, and before someone starts speaking, their name is shown on the screen. Employers, educators, event planners, and other accessibility specialists who want to fully involve with deaf and hard-of-hearing people can partner with AVA. With Ava, deaf and DHH people have a completely new degree of autonomy in many areas of everyday life.

5.5. VOXSCI

A voicemail-to-text tool called Voxsci turns voicemails into texts and emails that you can keep, search for, and share. Voicemails may be extremely difficult for listening to. By turning voicemail into text, VoxSciences offers a paradigm

improvement. With all the advantages that come with it, including texture search, audio communications now have a significant advantage over email, SMS, and instant messaging.

Voice transmissions are converted into text messages using the VERBS engine (virtual engine for basic language recognition), which then sends the text messages through email, SMS, or API. Voicemail to Text (SMS) solutions are perfect for home or business use. Call centers, comment or contest lines, and business voicemail systems are the major users of audio messages that are transcribed and sent through email.

A market research method called "The Client's Voice" offers a complete list of desires and client needs. It involves feedback analysis from a range of sources, including email surveys, the Internet, and IVR. VoxSciences offers an important service that makes it easier to analyze audio feedback for research by offering virtually real-time transcription of transcripts for the business class (Koshtura et. al., 2021).

6. Teachers' perspective

Having already mentioned in detail the necessity of access and implementation of ICT in curriculum of children with hearing disability, we should also highlight the imperative need for training teachers in use of assistive technologies in teaching deaf students. Many nations around the world have endorsed the use of Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) in the instruction of deaf students in the classroom. ICT and the mastery of key skills and concepts are understood and values in the educational "reality" as being equally important to reading, writing, and math proficiency (Keirungi, 2021). According to Ouma, Awuor and Kyambo (2013), many deaf students must be familiar with and proficient in ICT in order to participate in and benefit from educational programs.

Regarding a study carried out in Kabale, the capital of Uganda, various information is provided regarding the investigation of teachers' perceptions of the use of ICTs in teaching deaf students (Keirungi, 2021). The main purpose is to find out teachers' views about the use of ICT in deaf education, as well as the role of ICT in teaching deaf students along with the challenges teachers face when their educating programs are based on using technology methods. This led to the emergence of two entirely different viewpoints, according to which some teachers believe that ICT is a useful tool for instructing and communicating with students who have hearing impairments, while others believe that it is challenging to use and requires a lot of application time. However, deaf students are more likely to succeed in their educational program if they have access to the right ICT method (Keirungi, 2021).

Hameed (2009) reported that excellent learning opportunities are created for deaf students when they use visual forms which are less dependent on written language. ICT speeds up learning in many different ways. To prevent the child from falling behind other children in language development or acquisition, this interaction must be made sure of at a young age. Adequate computer labs and ICT equipment are important components in the use of ICT at schools for deaf. This will guarantee that teachers always have simple access to technology tools (Hennesy, Ruthven and Brindley, 2005). Turel and Johnson (2012) state that technical problems become a significant obstacle for teachers.

According to a survey conducted in all schools in Malaysia, including Sabah and Sarawak, where digital tools are used for teaching hearing-impaired children, it was found out that almost 90% of teachers concur that deaf students should take ICT lessons, compared to around 10% who disagree with this state (Nordin et al., 2015). Teachers recognized that their deaf students have great talent and knowledge, but due to a lack of computer equipment and busy schedule, they were not provided with ICT techniques. Since most schools don't computer classes or courses, the majority of teachers claimed that although students are very interested in computers, they haven't had the chance to use the most recent ICT technologies. It was enthusiastically supported by the teachers, who participated in this study that computer courses including visual media aids such as graphics, graphs and tables are crucial for individuals with hearing impairments. This is primarily due to teachers' beliefs that ICT courses supported by multimedia, attractive animations, and drawings, are more suitable for deaf students because they grab their attention visually more than plain, black and white lessons without visual media (Nordin et al., 2015).

Keirungi (2021) conducted a study to investigate teachers' perceptions of the use of ICT in teaching and learning process in the classroom of deaf students in Uganda in two Special Schools for Deaf in Kampala city. He tried to raise teachers' awareness of the value of ICT in teaching deaf students, serve as a source for other researchers looking to understand how ICT is used in classroom instruction, and inform implementers to compel teachers to use technology to improve learning process in deaf students (Keirungi, 2021). As a result, effective integration of ICTs depends on the perspectives of teachers and the leadership of the school. Older teachers in Kampala, who are accustomed to using traditional teaching techniques, do not want to switch to modern techniques. They are forced to using teaching-centered

approaches and face-to-face instructions, which give them a sense of authority in front of the students (Tedla, 2012; Makgato, 2012).

The main challenge is that teachers may not be able to use ICT effectively at the initial stage of lesson planning, neither to design interesting and attractive teaching strategies to guide deaf students to computer classes, which prevents them from actively participating in, discovering and learning about ICT (Keirungi, 2021). Positively, there is interest in flipped classroom models, which involve using computers and internet-based technologies in place of the traditional classroom (Amal, 2019). To improve learning opportunities and involve deaf students in the classroom, educators continually investigate new teaching strategies and styles (Zainuddin and Halili, 2016; Mehring and Leis, 2017).

Technology and communication strategies are clearly needed, and 21st century teachers need a set of specialized knowledge and abilities to use ICT in the classroom. According to several studies Mazlan, 2011; Mich, Pianta, & Mana, 2013 ICT should be taken into account to support hearing-impaired students learning. But teachers still don't use ICT (Chong and Shaffe, 2015). The teachers' knowledge and digital proficiency are crucial for maximizing the benefits of any technology initiatives. There was no predetermined framework for integrating technology into the curriculum previously, leaving educators uncertain about ICT and the pedagogy with which to incorporate it. To this end, a theoretical framework for integrating technology, pedagogy and content knowledge known as "TPACK" was created to instruct teachers in the development of ICT in schools (Amal, 2019).

7. Challenges and barriers

Learning ICT is vital to the development of deaf students, while ICT education (e-learning) enables them to diversify their learning preferences (Nordin et al., 2013). It is crucial that all people, especially deaf students, have access to these virtual learning environments and other educational technologies used in e-learning techniques.

According to Nordin et al. (2015) research, the challenges and obstacles faced by deaf students and teachers in the use of ICT in the education programs, are presented. They referred that communication between people with severe hearing problems and people with normal hearing can be very difficult. Most of the time, interpreters are rarely available outside of the classroom. Since the video for an online instruction on cooperation, communication and dissemination of information, the subtitles and video image of spoken text translation into sign language must be of suitable quality. Additionally, ICT (Information Communication Technology), which acts as a tool to modernize education system for deaf students, has the chance to enable new teaching and learning practices.

In the analysis of the research, only 7 schools in Malaysia provide ICT courses for hearing-impaired students (Nordin et al., 2015). The 17 other schools that do not offer ICT classes to students with hearing problems, have expressed their resentment and frustration over the fact that their students are not receiving an education in this field even though their students are really interested in it (Nordin et al., 2015).

In addition, visual display is crucial for deaf students, as only visual methods can help deaf students understand a particular task (Nordin et al., 2013). However, some of the barriers revealed, were: insufficient electronic devices, fear of using ICTs, lack of interest in learning ICT skills. A challenge in schools was also poor service delivery, inadequate budgeting for ICT maintenance and improper maintenance while also limited internet connectivity (Bingimlas, 2009). Internet access and inadequate ICT resources are the most major issues that schools for deaf students must deal with. But as already stated in the survey of Keirungi (2021), deaf schools in Uganda and whole Africa are not provided with many computers and ICT tools in classrooms to help deaf students to learn. At the same time, neither teachers nor students were given assistance to learn how to use and apply ICTs in learning process of deaf students.

Another obstacle that arises in the teaching of deaf students at King Saud University in Saudi Arabia, as Amal (2019) refers in his research, is that deaf students' interpreter occasionally translates incorrectly because they don't understand the scientific terms that were introduced in the lecture. So, Amal's research aims to address these barriers by implementing "flipped" classroom teaching method based on the integration of ICT in the teaching process, while also trying to enhance student learning quality.

Therefore, it is realized that deaf students face significant difficulties in the learning process through the integration of ICT in the educational program while misunderstandings are often created between teachers and sign language interpreters. At the same time, the limited supply of digital tools and computers in the classrooms leads students and teachers to avoid using ICT in their teaching. However, all students with hearing problems are entitled to equal rights in education for the purpose of future professional training and for this it is necessary to provide mandatory training to teachers in the use of ICT in the teaching program and to provide the necessary technological equipment.

8. Discussion

Finally, it's critical to emphasize the beneficial and influential role that digital technologies play in the field of education. Mobile devices (70-74), a range of ICT apps (75-87), AI & STEM ROBOTICS (88-102), and games (103-105) are examples of the technologies that facilitate and improve educational processes including evaluation, intervention, and learning. Additionally, the use of ICTs in combination with theories and models of metacognition, mindfulness, meditation, and the development of emotional intelligence [106-140], as well as with environmental factors and nutrition [66-69], speeds up and improves educational practices and results, especially for deaf students.

9. Conclusions

Taking into account the challenges and difficulties faced by deaf and hard of hearing people, it is important to emphasize that the use of ICT is essential for the educational, social and professional life of all people with or without disabilities. Thus, as summarized by the aforementioned research, a wealth of digital tools and applications have been created, which analyzed in detail in this research, aiming to help deaf and hard of hearing students overcome educational barriers, actively participate in society, develop their skills and most importantly have equal rights and opportunities with other people. However, as evidenced in many countries mainly in Africa, deaf students and citizens are not offered digital tools and computer lessons. Teachers do not have the knowledge and the education to integrate into the curriculum of deaf and hard of hearing students ICTs subjects and other technological tools. As a result, against the will and interest of deaf students to use ICTs in their learning process, lack of teachers training and limited technological equipment in their schools, makes use of ICTs impractical or sometimes ineffective.

Compliance with ethical standards

Acknowledgments

The Authors would like to thank their Teachers from the Postgraduate Degree Program for their guidance.

Disclosure of conflict of interest

The Authors proclaim no conflict of interest.

References

- [1] Akçayır, M., & Akçayır, G. (2017). Advantages and challenges associated with augmented reality for education: A systematic review of the literature. *Educational research review*, 20, 1-11.
- [2] Alazam, A. O., Bakar, A. R., Hamzah, R., & Asmiran, S. (2013). Teachers' ICT skills and ICT integration in the classroom: The case of vocational and technical teachers in Malaysia. *Creative Education*, 3(08), 70.
- [3] Alexander, B. (2006). Web 2.0: A new wave of innovation for teaching and learning? *Educause review*, 41(2), 33-34.
- [4] Al-Megren, S., & Almutairi, A. (2018). Assessing the effectiveness of an augmented reality application for the literacy development of Arabic children with hearing impairments. In *Cross-Cultural Design. Applications in Cultural Heritage, Creativity and Social Development: 10th International Conference, CCD 2018, Held as Part of HCI International 2018, Las Vegas, NV, USA, July 15-20, 2018, Proceedings, Part II 10* (pp. 3-18). Springer International Publishing.
- [5] Alnfai, M., & Sampali, S. (2017, September). Social and communication apps for the deaf and hearing impaired. In *2017 International Conference on Computer and Applications (ICCA)* (pp. 120-126). IEEE.
- [6] Amal, A. I. (2019). Deaf and hard of hearing students' perceptions of the flipped classroom strategy in an undergraduate education course. *European Journal of Educational Research*, 8(1), 325-336.
- [7] Anderson, P. (2007). *What is Web 2.0?: ideas, technologies and implications for education* (Vol. 1, No. 1, pp. 1-64). Bristol: JISC.
- [8] Azuma, R. T. (1997). A survey of augmented reality. *Presence: teleoperators & virtual environments*, 6(4), 355-385.

- [9] Barak, A., & Sadovsky, Y. (2008). Internet use and personal empowerment of hearing-impaired adolescents. *Computers in human behavior*, 24(5), 1802-1815.
- [10] Bingimlas, K. A. (2009). Barriers to the successful integration of ICT in teaching and learning environments: A review of the literature. *Eurasia Journal of Mathematics, science and technology education*, 5(3), 235-245.
- [11] Carr, D., Crook, C., Noss, R., Carmichael, P., & Selwyn, N. (2008). *Education 2.0? Designing the web for teaching and learning: A Commentary by the Technology Enhanced Learning phase of the Teaching and Learning Research Programme*, ISBN: 978-0-85473- 829-8
- [12] Constantinou, V., Ioannou, A., Klironomos, I., Antona, M., & Stephanidis, C. (2020). Technology support for the inclusion of deaf students in mainstream schools: a summary of research from 2007 to 2017. *Universal Access in the Information Society*, 19, 195-200.
- [13] Costello, R., Lambert, M., & Kern, F. (2019). How Can Accessibility for Deaf and Hearing-Impaired Players be Improved in Video Games? *International Journal of R&D Innovation Strategy*, 1, 16–32.
- [14] Chuck, L. & Geoff, F. (2000). *Techniques for Web Content Accessibility Guidelines 1.0*, W3C Note 6, <http://www.w3.org/TR/WAI-WEBCONTENT-TECHS>.
- [15] Dalsgaard, C. (2008). Social networking sites: Transparency in online education. In *EUNIS Congress*.
- [16] DeRaeve, L. (2010). Education and rehabilitation of deaf children with cochlear implants: a multidisciplinary task. *Cochlear Implants International*, 11(sup1), 7-14.
- [17] DeWitt, D., Alias, N., Ibrahim, Z., Shing, N., & Meeze, S. (2015). Design of a Learning Module for the Deaf in a Higher Education Institution Using Padlet. *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 176.
- [18] Drigas, A. S., Vrettaros, J., Stavrou, L., & Kouremenos, D. (2004). E-learning Environment for Deaf People in the E-commerce and New Technologies Sector. *WSEAS Transactions on Information Science and Applications*, 1(5), 1189-1196.
- [19] Drigas, A. S., Kouremenos, D., Kouremenos, S., & Vrettaros, J. (2005). An e-learning system for the deaf people. In *2005 6th International Conference on Information Technology Based Higher Education and Training* (pp. T2C-17). IEEE.
- [20] Drigas, A., Vrettaros, J., & Kouremenos, D. (2006). Web based teaching of English via Sign Language to Deaf people. In *IEEE's International Conference on Interactive Computer Aided Learning*.
- [21] Drigas, A., Kouremenos, D., Vrettaros, J., Karvounis, M., & Stavrou, P. (2009). The diagnosis of the educational needs of the hearing impaired. *International Journal of Social and Humanistic Computing*, 1(2), 138-148.
- [22] Drigas, A., Vrettaros, J., Tagoulis, A., & Kouremenos, D. (2010). Teaching a foreign language to deaf people via vodcasting & Web 2.0 tools. In *Organizational, Business, and Technological Aspects of the Knowledge Society: Third World Summit on the Knowledge Society, WSKS 2010, Corfu, Greece, September 22-24, 2010. Proceedings, Part II 3* (pp. 514-521). Springer Berlin Heidelberg.
- [23] Egaga, P.I. & Aderibigbe, S. A. (2015). Efficacy of Information and Communication Technology in enhancing learning outcomes of students with Hearing Impairment in Ibadan. *Journal of Education and Practice*, 6(30), pp. 202 – 205.
- [24] Embi, M.A., & Lubis, M.A. (2013). ICT in education for deaf learners: Teachers' perspective. *Research Journal of Applied Sciences*, 8(2), pp. 103-111.
- [25] Hameed, A. (2009). Information and communication technologies as a new learning tool for the deaf. *Relation*, 10(1.129), pp.7856.
- [26] Hennessy, S., Ruthven, K., & Brindley, S. U. E. (2005). Teacher perspectives on integrating ICT into subject teaching: commitment, constraints, caution, and change. *Journal of curriculum studies*, 37(2), 155-192.
- [27] Hyde, M., Punch, R., Power, D., Hartley, J., Neale, J., & Brennan, L. (2009). The experiences of deaf and hard of hearing students at a Queensland University: 1985–2005. *Higher Education Research & Development*, 28(1), 85-98.
- [28] Juul, J. (2010). *A casual revolution: Reinventing video games and their players*. MIT press.
- [29] Gibson, I. S., O'Reilly, C., & Hughes, M. (2002). Integration of ICT within a project-based learning environment. *European journal of engineering education*, 27(1), 21-30.

- [30] Glaser, M., & Tucker, W. D. (2004). Telecommunications bridging between Deaf and hearing users in South Africa. Proc. Conference and Workshop on Assistive Technologies for Vision and Hearing Impairment (CVHI 2004), Granada, Spain.
- [31] Keirungi, J. (2021). Teachers' perceptions on the use of information and Communication technology in the teaching of deaf learners: a case of two primary schools in Kampala capital city, Uganda (Doctoral dissertation, Kyambogo University).
- [32] Kelman, C. A., & Branco, A. U. (2009). (Meta)communication Strategies in Inclusive Classes for Deaf Students. *American Annals of the Deaf*, 154(4), 371–381
- [33] Koshtura, D., Andrunyk, V., & Shestakevych, T. (2021). Development of a Speech-to-Text Program for People with Haring Impairments. In *MoMLet+ DS* (pp. 565-583).
- [34] Kosmopoulos, D., Constantinopoulos, C., Trigka, M., Papazachariou, D., Antzakas, K., Lampropoulou, V., ... & Moneda, A. (2022). Museum Guidance in Sign Language: The SignGuide project. In *Proceedings of the 15th International Conference on PErvasive Technologies Related to Assistive Environments* (pp. 646-652).
- [35] Lee, S., Henderson, V., Brashear, H., Starner, T., & Hamilton, S. (2005). User-centered development of a gesture-based American Sign Language game. Paper presented at the Instructional Technology and Education of the Deaf Symposium, Rochester, NY.
- [36] Lee, H. S., & Lee, J. W. (2008). Mathematical education game based on augmented reality. In *Technologies for E-Learning and Digital Entertainment: Third International Conference, Edutainment 2008 Nanjing, China, June 25-27, 2008 Proceedings 3* (pp. 442-450). Springer Berlin Heidelberg.
- [37] Li, J., Van der Spek, E. D., Feijs, L., Wang, F., & Hu, J. (2017). Augmented reality games for learning: A literature review. In *Distributed, Ambient and Pervasive Interactions: 5th International Conference, DAPI 2017, Held as Part of HCI International 2017, Vancouver, BC, Canada, July 9–14, 2017, Proceedings 5* (pp. 612-626). Springer International Publishing.
- [38] Luo, L., Weng, D., Songrui, G., Hao, J., & Tu, Z. (2022, April). Avatar interpreter: improving classroom experiences for deaf and hard-of-hearing people based on augmented reality. In *CHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems Extended Abstracts* (pp. 1-5).
- [39] Makgato, M. (2012). Status of teachers' use of educational technology: a case of some schools in South African semi-urban locations. *International Proceedings of Economics Development and Research-Business and Economics Research*, 47.
- [40] Mazlan, N. H. (2011). Development and evaluation of an electronic signing storybook for enhancing reading among deaf students (Master's thesis). Universiti Putra Malaysia. Retrieved from <http://psasir.upm.edu.my/id/eprint/32551/>
- [41] Mehring, J., & Leis, A. (2018). Innovations in flipping the language classroom. *Innovations in Flipping the Language Classroom: Theories and Practices*. Springer.
- [42] Mich, O., Pianta, E., & Mana, N. (2013). Interactive stories and exercises with dynamic feedback for improving reading comprehension skills in deaf children. *Computers & Education*, 65, 34-44.
- [43] Nordin, N., Yunus, M. M., Zaharudin, R., Salehi, H., Mohd Yasin, M. H., & Embi, M. A. (2015). Identifying the challenges and barriers hearing-impaired learners face with using ICT education courses. *Journal of Theoretical & Applied Information Technology*, 78(3).
- [44] Nordin, N., Zaharudin, R., Yasin, M. H. M., & Lubis, M. A. (2013). Students' View on the ICT Courses Specially-Designed for the Deaf Learners. *Asian Social Science*, 9(12), 13.
- [45] Offermans, S., & Hu, J. (2013). Augmented home: integrating a virtual world game in a physical environment. In *Entertainment Computing-ICEC 2013: 12th International Conference, ICEC 2013, São Paulo, Brazil, October 16-18, 2013. Proceedings 12* (pp. 30-35). Springer Berlin Heidelberg.
- [46] Ouma, G. O., Awuor, F. M., & Kyambo, B. (2013). E-Learning readiness in Public Secondary Schools in Kenya. *European Journal of Open,Distance and ELearning*,16(2),pp.97-110.
- [47] Parton, B. S., Hancock, R., & Dawson, J. (2010). Augmented reality for deaf students: Can mobile devices make it possible?. In *Human-Computer Interaction: Second IFIP TC 13 Symposium, HCIS 2010, Held as Part of WCC 2010, Brisbane, Australia, September 20-23, 2010. Proceedings* (pp. 309-312). Springer Berlin Heidelberg.

- [48] Peng, C., & Daud, S. (2015, July). Exploring elementary special education (hearing impairment) teachers' technological pedagogical content knowledge (TPACK). In 1st International Conference on Special Education, Bangkok, Thailand (pp. 28-31).
- [49] Ridha, A. M., & Shehieb, W. (2021). Assistive technology for hearing-impaired and deaf students utilizing augmented reality. In 2021 IEEE Canadian Conference on Electrical and Computer Engineering (CCECE) (pp. 1-5). IEEE.
- [50] Power, D., & Power, M. R. (2009). Communication and culture: signing deaf people online in Europe. *Technology and Disability*, 21(4), 127-134.
- [51] Quintero, J., Baldiris, S., Rubira, R., Cerón, J., & Velez, G. (2019). Augmented reality in educational inclusion. A systematic review on the last decade. *Frontiers in psychology*, 10, 1835.
- [52] Sanger, L.M. (2006) 'The future of free information', *Digital Universe Journal*, No. 2006-1, Digital Universe Foundation.
- [53] Seely Brown, J., & Adler, R. P. (2008). Open education, the long tail, and learning 2.0. *Educause review*, 43(1), 16-20.
- [54] Squire, K. D., & Jan, M. (2007). Mad city mystery: Developing scientific argumentation skills with a place-based augmented reality game on handheld computers. *Journal of science education and technology*, 16, 5-29.
- [55] Suszczanska, N. (2002). Translating Polish texts into sign language in the TGT system. Paper presented at the 20th IASTED Conference on Applied Informatics, Innsbruck, Australia.
- [56] Swain, J. and French, S. (2004) 'Disability and communication: listening is not enough', in Barrett, S., Komarony, C., Robb, M. and Rogers, A. (Eds.): *Communication, Relationships and Care: A Reader*, pp. 220–234.
- [57] Tedla, B.A. (2012). Understanding the importance, impacts and barriers of ICT on teaching and learning in East African countries. *International Journal for e-Learning Security (IJeLS)*, 2(3/4), pp. 199-207.
- [58] Turel, Y. K., & Johnson, T. E. (2012). Teachers' Belief and Use of Interactive Whiteboards for Teaching and Learning. *Educational Technology & Society*. 15(1). 381–394.
- [59] Tze, C. O., Filntisis, P. P., Dimou, A. L., Roussos, A., & Maragos, P. (2022). Neural Sign Reenactor: Deep Photorealistic Sign Language Retargeting. DOI:10.48550/arXiv.2209.01470
- [60] Westin, T., Neves, J., Mozelius, P., Sousa, C., & Mantovan, L. (2022). Inclusive AR-games for Education of Deaf Children: Challenges and Opportunities. In *European Conference on Games Based Learning* (Vol. 16, No. 1, pp. 597-604).
- [61] Zaharudin, R., Nordin, N. M., Yasin, M. H. M., Din, R., & Embi, M. A. (2011). Observation on the deaf students' interaction in learning ICT-courses. *Proceedings of the 10th WSEAS e-Activities*.
- [62] Zaharudin, R., Nordin, N. M., Yasin, M. H. M., Din, R., & Embi, M. A. (2011). Exploring teachers' insight on ICT education via e-learning for the deaf learners. In *Proc. of the 10th WSEAS Int. Conf. on E-Activities* (pp. 52-58). World Scientific and Engineering Academy and Society (WSEAS).
- [63] Zainuddin, N. M. M., Zaman, H. B., & Ahmad, A. (2010). Developing augmented reality book for deaf in science: the determining factors. In *2010 International Symposium on Information Technology* (Vol. 1, pp. 1-4). IEEE.
- [64] Zainuddin, Z., & Halili, S. H. (2016). Flipped classroom research and trends from different fields of study. *The International Review of Research in Open and Distributed Learning*, 17(3). doi:10.19173/irrodl.v17i3.2274
- [65] Stavridou Th., Driga, A.M., Drigas, A.S., 2021. Blood Markers in Detection of Autism, *International Journal of Recent Contributions from Engineering Science & IT (ijES)* 9(2):79-86. <https://doi.org/10.3991/ijes.v9i2.21283>
- [66] Zavitsanou, A., & Drigas, A. (2021). Nutrition in mental and physical health. *Technium Soc. Sci. J.*, 23, 67. <https://doi.org/10.47577/tssj.v23i1.4126>
- [67] Driga, A.M., Drigas, A.S. 2019 "Climate Change 101: How Everyday Activities Contribute to the Ever-Growing Issue", *International Journal of Recent Contributions from Engineering, Science & IT*, vol. 7(1), pp. 22-31. <https://doi.org/10.3991/ijes.v7i1.10031>
- [68] Driga, A.M., and Drigas, A.S. 2019 "ADHD in the Early Years: Pre-Natal and Early Causes and Alternative Ways of Dealing." *International Journal of Online and Biomedical Engineering (IJOE)*, vol. 15, no. 13, p. 95., doi:10.3991/ijoe.v15i13.11203

- [69] Stathopoulou, et al 2018, Mobile assessment procedures for mental health and literacy skills in education. *International Journal of Interactive Mobile Technologies*, 12(3), 21-37, <https://doi.org/10.3991/ijim.v12i3.8038>
- [70] Kokkalia G, AS Drigas, A Economou 2016 Mobile learning for preschool education. *International Journal of Interactive Mobile Technologies* 10 (4), 57-64 <https://doi.org/10.3991/ijim.v10i4.6021>
- [71] Stathopoulou A, Karabatzaki Z, Tsiros D, Katsantoni S, Drigas A, 2019 Mobile apps the educational solution for autistic students in secondary education *Journal of Interactive Mobile Technologies* 13 (2), 89-101 <https://doi.org/10.3991/ijim.v13i02.9896>
- [72] Drigas A, DE Dede, S Dedes 2020 Mobile and other applications for mental imagery to improve learning disabilities and mental health *International Journal of Computer Science Issues (IJCSI)* 17 (4), 18-23, DOI:10.5281/zenodo.3987533
- [73] Alexopoulou A, Batsou A, Drigas A, 2020 Mobiles and cognition: The associations between mobile technology and cognitive flexibility *ijIM* 14(3) 146-15, <https://doi.org/10.3991/ijim.v14i03.11233>
- [74] Drigas, A. S., J.Vrettaros, L.Stavrou, D.Kouremenos, 2004. E-learning Environment for Deaf people in the E-Commerce and New Technologies Sector, *WSEAS Transactions on Information Science and Applications*, Issue 5, Volume 1, November
- [75] Drigas, A., Koukianakis, L., Papagerasimou, Y., 2011, Towards an ICT-based psychology: Epsychology, *Computers in Human Behavior*, 27:1416–1423. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chb.2010.07.045>
- [76] Papanastasiou, G., Drigas, A., Skianis, C., and Lytras, M. (2020). Brain computer interface based applications for training and rehabilitation of students with neurodevelopmental disorders. A literature review. *Heliyon* 6:e04250. doi: 10.1016/j.heliyon.2020.e04250
- [77] Drigas, A. S., John Vrettaros, and Dimitris Kouremenos, 2005. "An e-learning management system for the deaf people," *AIKED '05: Proceedings of the Fourth WSEAS International Conference on Artificial Intelligence, Knowledge Engineering Data Bases*, article number 28.
- [78] Drigas, A., & Papanastasiou, G. (2014). Interactive White Boards in Preschool and Primary Education. *International Journal of Online and Biomedical Engineering (ijOE)*, 10(4), 46–51. <https://doi.org/10.3991/ijoe.v10i4.3754>
- [79] Drigas, A. S. and Politi-Georgousi, S. (2019). ICTs as a distinct detection approach for dyslexia screening: A contemporary view. *International Journal of Online and Biomedical Engineering (ijOE)*, 15(13):46–60. <https://doi.org/10.3991/ijoe.v15i13.11011>
- [80] Drigas A, Petrova A 2014 ICTs in speech and language therapy *International Journal of Engineering Pedagogy (ijEP)* 4 (1), 49-54 <https://doi.org/10.3991/ijep.v4i1.3280>
- [81] Bravou V, Oikonomidou D, Drigas A, 2022 Applications of Virtual Reality for Autism Inclusion. A review *Retos* 45, 779-785 <https://doi.org/10.47197/retos.v45i0.92078>
- [82] Chaidi I, Drigas A, 2022 "Parents' views Questionnaire for the education of emotions in Autism Spectrum Disorder" in a Greek context and the role of ICTs *Technium Social Sciences Journal* 33, 73-9, DOI:10.47577/tssj.v33i1.6878
- [83] Bravou V, Drigas A, 2019 A contemporary view on online and web tools for students with sensory & learning disabilities *ijOE* 15(12) 97 <https://doi.org/10.3991/ijoe.v15i12.10833>
- [84] Drigas A, Vrettaros J, Tagoulis A, Kouremenos D, 2010 Teaching a foreign language to deaf people via vodcasting & web 2.0 tools *World Summit on Knowledge Society*, 514-521 DOI:10.1007/978-3-642-16324-1_60
- [85] Chaidi I, Drigas A, C Karagiannidis 2021 ICT in special education *Technium Soc. Sci. J.* 23, 187, <https://doi.org/10.47577/tssj.v23i1.4277>
- [86] Xanthopoulou M, Kokalia G, Drigas A, 2019, Applications for Children with Autism in Preschool and Primary Education. *Int. J. Recent Contributions Eng. Sci. IT* 7 (2), 4-16, <https://doi.org/10.3991/ijes.v7i2.10335>
- [87] Chaidi E, Kefalis C, Papagerasimou Y, Drigas, 2021, Educational robotics in Primary Education. A case in Greece, *Research, Society and Development* 10 (9), e17110916371-e17110916371, <https://doi.org/10.33448/rsd-v10i9.16371>
- [88] Drigas, A.S., Vrettaros, J., Koukianakis, L.G. and Glentzes, J.G. (2005). A Virtual Lab and e-learning system for renewable energy sources. *Int. Conf. on Educational Tech.*

- [89] Lytra N, Drigas A 2021 STEAM education-metacognition–Specific Learning Disabilities Scientific Electronic Archives 14 (10) <https://doi.org/10.36560/141020211442>
- [90] Mitsea E, Lytra N, A Akrivopoulou, A Drigas 2020 Metacognition, Mindfulness and Robots for Autism Inclusion. *Int. J. Recent Contributions Eng. Sci. IT* 8 (2), 4-20. <https://doi.org/10.3991/ijes.v8i2.14213>
- [91] Stavridis S, D Papageorgiou, Z Doulgeri 2017 Dynamical system based robotic motion generation with obstacle avoidance, *IEEE Robotics and Automation Letters* 2 (2), 712-718, DOI:10.1109/LRA.2017.2651172
- [92] Kastritsi T, D Papageorgiou, I Sarantopoulos, S Stavridis, Z Doulgeri, 2019 Guaranteed active constraints enforcement on point cloud-approximated regions for surgical applications 2019 International Conference on Robotics and Automation (ICRA), 8346-8352 DOI:10.1109/ICRA.2019.8793953
- [93] Stavridis S, Z Doulgeri 2018 Bimanual assembly of two parts with relative motion generation and task related optimization 2018 IEEE/RSJ International Conference on Intelligent Robots and Systems
- [94] DOI:10.1109/IROS.2018.8593928
- [95] Stavridis S, P Falco, Z Doulgeri 2020 Pick-and-place in dynamic environments with a mobile dual-arm robot equipped with distributed distance sensors IEEE-RAS 20th International Conference on Humanoid Robots (Humanoids) DOI: 10.1109/HUMANOIDS47582.2021.9555672
- [96] Papageorgiou D, S Stavridis, C Papakonstantinou, Z Doulgeri 2021 Task geometry aware assistance for kinesthetic teaching of redundant robots IEEE/RSJ International Conference on Intelligent Robots and Systems (IROS), Prague, Czech Republic, 2021, pp. 7285–7291. <https://doi.org/10.1109/IROS51168.2021.9636209>
- [97] Kastritsi T, I Sarantopoulos, S Stavridis, D Papageorgiou, Z Doulgeri Manipulation of a Whole Surgical Tool Within Safe Regions Utilizing Barrier Artificial Potentials Mediterranean Conference on Medical and Biological Engineering and Computing DOI:10.1007/978-3-030-31635-8_193
- [98] Stavridis S, D Papageorgiou, L Droukas, Z Doulgeri 2022 Bimanual crop manipulation for human-inspired robotic harvesting <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2209.06074>
- [99] Stavridis S, Papageorgiou D, Zoe Doulgeri, 2022, Kinesthetic teaching of bi-manual tasks with known relative constraints, Conference: 2022 IEEE/RSJ International Conference on Intelligent Robots and Systems (IROS-2022) Kyoto, Japan
- [100] Ntaountaki P, et al 2019 Robotics in Autism Intervention. *Int. J. Recent Contributions Eng. Sci. IT* 7 (4), 4-17, <https://doi.org/10.3991/ijes.v7i4.11448>
- [101] Demertzi E, Voukelatos N, Papagerasimou Y, Drigas A, 2018 Online learning facilities to support coding and robotics courses for youth *International Journal of Engineering Pedagogy (ijEP)* 8 (3), 69-80, <https://doi.org/10.3991/ijep.v8i3.8044>
- [102] Drigas A, Kouremenos S, Vrettos S, Vrettaros J, Kouremenos S, 2004 An expert system for job matching of the unemployed *Expert Systems with Applications* 26 (2), 217-224 [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0957-4174\(03\)00136-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0957-4174(03)00136-2)
- [103] Chaidi I, Drigas A 2022 Digital games & special education *Technium Social Sciences Journal* 34, 214-236 <https://doi.org/10.47577/tssj.v34i1.7054>
- [104] Doulou A, Drigas A 2022 Electronic, VR & Augmented Reality Games for Intervention in ADHD *Technium Social Sciences Journal*, 28, 159. <https://doi.org/10.47577/tssj.v28i1.5728>
- [105] Kefalis C, Kontostavlou EZ, Drigas A, 2020 The Effects of Video Games in Memory and Attention. *Int. J. Eng. Pedagog.* 10 (1), 51-61, <https://doi.org/10.3991/ijep.v10i1.11290>
- [106] Drigas, A., & Mitsea, E. (2020). The 8 Pillars of Metacognition. *International Journal of Emerging Technologies in Learning (ijET)*, 15(21), 162-178. <https://doi.org/10.3991/ijet.v15i21.14907>
- [107] Drigas, A. S., and M. Pappas, 2017. “The Consciousness-Intelligence-Knowledge Pyramid: An 8x8 Layer Model,” *International Journal of Recent Contributions from Engineering, Science & IT (ijES)*, vol. 5, no.3, pp 14-25, <https://doi.org/10.3991/ijes.v5i3.7680>
- [108] Drigas A, Karyotaki M (2017) Attentional control and other executive functions. *Int J Emerg Technol Learn ijET* 12(03):219–233 <https://doi.org/10.3991/ijet.v12i03.6587>
- [109] Drigas A, Karyotaki M 2014. Learning Tools and Application for Cognitive Improvement. *International Journal of Engineering Pedagogy*, 4(3): 71-77. <https://doi.org/10.3991/ijep.v4i3.3665>

- [110] Drigas, A., & Mitsea, E. (2021). 8 Pillars X 8 Layers Model of Metacognition: Educational Strategies, Exercises & Trainings. *International Journal of Online & Biomedical Engineering*, 17(8). <https://doi.org/10.3991/ijoe.v17i08.23563>
- [111] Drigas A., Papoutsis C. (2020). The Need for Emotional Intelligence Training Education in Critical and Stressful Situations: The Case of COVID-19. *Int. J. Recent Contrib. Eng. Sci. IT* 8(3), 20–35. <https://doi.org/10.3991/ijes.v8i3.17235>
- [112] Kokkalia, G., Drigas, A., Economou, A., & Roussos, P. (2019). School readiness from kindergarten to primary school. *International Journal of Emerging Technologies in Learning*, 14(11), 4-18. <https://doi.org/10.3991/ijet.v14i11.10090>
- [113] Papoutsis, C. and Drigas, A. (2017) Empathy and Mobile Applications. *International Journal of Interactive Mobile Technologies* 11(3). 57. <https://doi.org/10.3991/ijim.v11i3.6385>
- [114] Angelopoulou, E., Drigas, A. (2021). Working Memory, Attention and their Relationship: A theoretical Overview. *Research. Society and Development*, 10(5), 1-8. <https://doi.org/10.33448/rsd-v10i5.15288>
- [115] Drigas A, Mitsea E 2020 A metacognition based 8 pillars mindfulness model and training strategies. *International Journal of Recent Contributions from Engineering, Science & IT* 8(4), 4-17. <https://doi.org/10.3991/ijes.v8i4.17419>
- [116] Papoutsis C, Drigas A, C Skianis 2021 Virtual and augmented reality for developing emotional intelligence skills *Int. J. Recent Contrib. Eng. Sci. IT (IJES)* 9 (3), 35-53. <https://doi.org/10.3991/ijes.v9i3.23939>
- [117] Kapsi S, Katsantoni S, Drigas A 2020 The Role of Sleep and Impact on Brain and Learning. *Int. J. Recent Contributions Eng. Sci. IT* 8 (3), 59-68. <https://doi.org/10.3991/ijes.v8i3.17099>
- [118] Drigas A, Mitsea E, Skianis C 2021 The Role of Clinical Hypnosis & VR in Special Education *International Journal of Recent Contributions from Engineering Science & IT (IJES)* 9(4), 4-18. <https://doi.org/10.3991/ijes.v9i4.26147>
- [119] V Galitskaya, A Drigas 2021 The importance of working memory in children with Dyscalculia and Ageometria *Scientific Electronic Archives* 14 (10) <https://doi.org/10.36560/141020211449>
- [120] Chaidi I, Drigas A 2020 Parents' Involvement in the Education of their Children with Autism: Related Research and its Results *International Journal Of Emerging Technologies In Learning (Ijet)* 15 (14), 194-203. <https://doi.org/10.3991/ijet.v15i14.12509>
- [121] Drigas A, Mitsea E 2021 Neuro-Linguistic Programming & VR via the 8 Pillars of Metacognition X 8 Layers of Consciousness X 8 Intelligences *Technium Soc. Sci. J.* 26(1), 159–176. <https://doi.org/10.47577/tssj.v26i1.5273>
- [122] Drigas A, Mitsea E 2022 Conscious Breathing: a Powerful Tool for Physical & Neuropsychological Regulation. The role of Mobile Apps *Technium Social Sciences Journal* 28, 135-158. <https://doi.org/10.47577/tssj.v28i1.5922>
- [123] Drigas A, Mitsea E, C Skianis 2022 Clinical Hypnosis & VR, Subconscious Restructuring-Brain Rewiring & the Entanglement with the 8 Pillars of Metacognition X 8 Layers of Consciousness X 8 Intelligences. *International Journal of Online & Biomedical Engineering (IJOE)* 18 (1), 78-95. <https://doi.org/10.3991/ijoe.v18i01.26859>
- [124] Drigas A, Karyotaki M 2019 Attention and its Role: Theories and Models. *International Journal of Emerging Technologies in Learning* 14 (12), 169-182, <https://doi.org/10.3991/ijet.v14i12.10185>
- [125] Drigas A, Karyotaki M 2019 Executive Functioning and Problem Solving: A Bidirectional Relation. *International Journal of Engineering Pedagogy (ijEP)* 9 (3) <https://doi.org/10.3991/ijep.v9i3.10186>
- [126] Bamicha V, Drigas A 2022 ToM & ASD: The interconnection of Theory of Mind with the social-emotional, cognitive development of children with Autism Spectrum Disorder. The use of ICTs as an alternative form of intervention in ASD *Technium Social Sciences Journal* 33, 42-72, <https://doi.org/10.47577/tssj.v33i1.6845>
- [127] Drigas A, Mitsea E, C Skianis 2022 Neuro-Linguistic Programming, Positive Psychology & VR in Special Education. *Scientific Electronic Archives* 15 (1) <https://doi.org/10.36560/15120221497>
- [128] Drigas A, Mitsea E, Skianis C. 2022 Virtual Reality and Metacognition Training Techniques for Learning Disabilities *SUSTAINABILITY* 14(16), 10170, <https://doi.org/10.3390/su141610170>
- [129] Drigas A., Sideraki A. 2021 Emotional Intelligence in Autism *Technium Soc. Sci. J.* 26, 80, <https://doi.org/10.47577/tssj.v26i1.5178>

- [130] Drigas A, Mitsea E, Skianis C.. 2022 Subliminal Training Techniques for Cognitive, Emotional and Behavioural Balance. The role of Emerging Technologies Technium Social Sciences Journal 33, 164-186, <https://doi.org/10.47577/tssj.v33i1.6881>
- [131] Bakola L, Drigas A, 2020 Technological development process of emotional Intelligence as a therapeutic recovery implement in children with ADHD and ASD comorbidity. . International Journal of Online & Biomedical Engineering, 16(3), 75-85, <https://doi.org/10.3991/ijoe.v16i03.12877>
- [132] Bamicha V, Drigas A, 2022 The Evolutionary Course of Theory of Mind - Factors that facilitate or inhibit its operation & the role of ICTs Technium Social Sciences Journal 30, 138-158, DOI:10.47577/tssj.v30i1.6220
- [133] Karyotaki M, Bakola L, Drigas A, Skianis C, 2022 Women's Leadership via Digital Technology and Entrepreneurship in business and society Technium Social Sciences Journal. 28(1), 246–252. <https://doi.org/10.47577/tssj.v28i1.5907>
- [134] Drigas A, Bakola L, 2021The 8x8 Layer Model Consciousness-Intelligence-Knowledge Pyramid, and the Platonic Perspectives International Journal of Recent Contributions from Engineering, Science & IT (ijES) 9(2) 57-72, <https://doi.org/10.3991/ijes.v9i2.22497>
- [135] Drigas A, Karyotaki M, 2016 Online and Other ICT-based Training Tools for Problem-solving Skills. International Journal of Emerging Technologies in Learning 11 (6) <https://doi.org/10.3991/ijet.v11i06.5340>
- [136] Mitsea E, Drigas A,, Skianis C, 2022 Breathing, Attention & Consciousness in Sync: The role of Breathing Training, Metacognition & Virtual Reality Technium Social Sciences Journal 29, 79-97, <https://doi.org/10.47577/tssj.v29i1.6145>
- [137] Mitsea E, Drigas A, Skianis C, 2022 ICTs and Speed Learning in Special Education: High-Consciousness Training Strategies for High-Capacity Learners through Metacognition Lens Technium Soc. Sci. J. 27, 230, <https://doi.org/10.47577/tssj.v27i1.5599>
- [138] Drigas A, Karyotaki M, Skianis C, 2017 Success: A 9 layered-based model of giftedness International Journal of Recent Contributions from Engineering, Science & IT 5(4) 4-18, <https://doi.org/10.3991/ijes.v5i4.7725>
- [139] Drigas A, Papoutsi C, 2021,Nine Layer Pyramid Model Questionnaire for Emotional Intelligence, International Journal of Online & Biomedical Engineering 17 (7), <https://doi.org/10.3991/ijoe.v17i07.22765>
- [140] Drigas A, Papoutsi C, Skianis, 2021, Metacognitive and Metaemotional Training Strategies through the Nine-layer Pyramid Model of Emotional Intelligence, International Journal of Recent Contributions from Engineering, Science & IT (ijES) 9.4 58-76, <https://doi.org/10.3991/ijes.v9i4.26189>